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Bias types and patterns: a typology applied to Europeana use cases

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Executive Summary

The DE-BIAS project examines how bias manifests in cultural metadata and provides cultural heritage professionals with tools to identify and address problematic terminology and descriptions. This *Typology* summarises key findings and presents a practical framework for understanding and addressing bias in digital cultural heritage collections.

As cultural heritage institutions increasingly digitise their collections for broader audiences, the need to carefully examine and contextualise potentially harmful language in metadata becomes more urgent. Rather than advocating for removal of problematic terms, DE-BIAS promotes adding contextual layers that acknowledge historical perspectives while ensuring a respectful representation of communities.

Through analysis of Europeana collections and collaboration with community groups, the project has developed a systematic approach to identifying bias across multiple dimensions. This approach recognizes that bias often occurs at intersections of different categories (such as gender, ethnicity, and religion) and requires nuanced understanding of both historical contexts and contemporary sensitivities.

Core Takeaways

1. Understanding bias location
 - Linguistic level (terminology, descriptions)
 - Visual level (representation, framing)
 - Relationship between linguistic and visual elements
2. Recognizing complexity
 - Intersectionality of different bias types
 - Historical context and temporal layers
 - Community perspectives and impact
3. Moving forward
 - Community collaboration is essential
 - Bias detection tools need human oversight
 - Continuous evolution of practices required

This *Typology* serves as a practical guide for cultural heritage professionals seeking to make their digital collections more inclusive and respectfully representative of diverse communities. The document provides frameworks, examples, and actionable recommendations that institutions can adapt to their specific contexts and needs.

Introduction

Since 2011, in line with the European Commission's digitisation policy, many cultural heritage institutions (CHIs) in Europe have published digitised collections online. These online publications, many of which have been aggregated by Europeana¹ - the gateway to digital collections from across the continent - are made accessible using metadata based on the original catalogue descriptions, in some cases with additional metadata enrichment.

While neither contributing CHIs or content aggregators² can be held responsible for the content of the heritage objects themselves - for example, the opinions expressed or the wording used in a digitised historical newspaper article or source document - they are responsible for (or at least should be aware of) the metadata associated with these objects. Indeed, as a project consortium firmly rooted and intertwined with the sector, we have witnessed a growing need with CHIs to ensure that this metadata does not contain inappropriate or harmful expressions, or at least to be able to signal possible contentious issues. This is even more important when digitised collections are made available online to a wide and diverse audience to encourage consultation and reuse. As cultural heritage (CH) - and therefore the types of data that are considered cultural heritage - and audiences evolve, we need to be aware that what is or could be considered harmful is constantly and necessarily subject to change.

This *Typology* outlines different types of bias found in CH collections and object descriptions. We examine concepts such as intentionality, dimensionality and intersectionality, together offering a framework for understanding how and where bias in (descriptions of) cultural collections can occur and what could be the criteria for assessing the urgency and priority of mitigation, prevention or solution strategies. Our research has been fed by cross-referencing academic writings and theories on the topic of bias in the use of language with cultural content published to Europeana. The examples help to clarify what kind of issues are commonly found and at which levels expressions of bias tend to occur. Based on our research and the applicative remit provided by Europeana, we transpose the proposed framework for understanding bias into a graph to be used by CH practitioners and other stakeholders as a tool for analysing, assessing and addressing bias occurrences. Yet first, to effectively address bias in cultural metadata, we must understand several key concepts and considerations that shape how bias manifests and is interpreted in cultural heritage collections.

¹ www.europeana.eu

² Aggregators: organisations working with cultural heritage institutions to gather, prepare, transform, enrich and publish their data with a view to making collections accessible through portals such as Europeana.eu.

1. Key concepts and considerations

? Key questions answered in this section

- Why is bias in cultural metadata an urgent issue for heritage institutions?
- How does digitization change the impact of biased metadata?
- What role do communities play in addressing metadata bias?
- How do historical context and present-day sensitivities interact?

1.1 Positionality vs. Neutrality

Archives, libraries and museums have been housing CH collections for centuries. During this long period, cultural objects have not only been catalogued, used, preserved and described by heritage institutions, but have also been endowed with meanings and functions that have contributed to their definition and perception. These meanings and descriptions are always characterised by 'positionality': they are the inevitable expression of a constellation of socio-historical dynamics, cultural backgrounds and belief systems. Positionality is also linked to power differentials: even when institutions claim and assume to be neutral and objective, their perspective is always shaped by the ideology and hegemonic values of a particular society. This explains why words and images that are not considered offensive at one point in time may be perceived very differently by users at a later time or by a different group or community.

This questioning of assumed, self-evident neutrality in the twentieth century arose in the wake of a growing awareness that discrimination is often accompanied and sustained by widespread linguistic bias against certain groups. The first major axes of difference in power and status to be discussed were class, race and gender. These coincided with the rise of global emancipatory and/or political struggles such as socialism, communism, anti-fascism, anti-racism, decolonialism, feminism and civil rights movements. All of these strands of activism have counterparts in systems of thought that continue to influence not only the humanities but also the sciences as a whole. In the wake of these three main markers of identity, other axes of discrimination have been identified, such as sexuality, ethnicity, age, (dis)ability and religion.

Sensitivity and attention to the offensive power of certain words and terms are an important part of raising awareness and have led to the replacement of certain terms. However, as language and power dynamics are continuously evolving, they are also subject to significant change. Words or terms that were prevalent in one period, such as "Eskimo" or "handicapped", may be considered biased in another. Conversely, terms

that were once considered derogatory - such as “punk” or “queer” - may later be adopted or re-appropriated by certain groups as a badge of honour, although it should be noted that the use of these terms is usually reserved for members of the group and cannot always be appropriated indiscriminately.

Examples:

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/92026/pamphlets_dasmaa_2008_feb_partiprogrammer_object70968

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/9200235/download_type_document_docid_574668

- Context: Political pamphlet, academic study and conference announcement referring to "queer".
- Bias Analysis: These cases illustrate that interpreting the meaning of the term "queer" or the assessment of the intentionality and harm of use requires knowledge of who is actually using it, and what their purpose would be. This knowledge is not always available in the often sparse metadata connected to digital records.

1.2 More Than Words

As mentioned above, bias, misrepresentations and misinterpretations of CH objects are pervasive, not only from a terminological point of view - words appearing in object descriptions - but also at a deeper metadata level. The temporal complexity of metadata must be taken into account as well. Biases can arise both within and as a result of the cataloguing and digitisation processes, for example in the categorisation of information or in the way metadata is structured. Because Dublin Core serves as the structural basis for metadata provision in many galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAMs), the default assumption is that a work always has an 'author/creator' and a title. This way of structuring data makes it difficult to encode, for example, First Nations or other community heritage collections where valuable items are not expected to have an identifiable 'author' or 'creator'.

This is compounded by the layered and iterative process by which digital objects are wrapped in information, as in many cases further metadata is added to the original descriptions by the cataloguer or archivist, often on the basis of controlled vocabularies, which tend to be biased as well.

Poster for the documentary *Change the Subject* about Dartmouth College students lobbying the Library of Congress. Sawyer Broadley, with Jill Baron, Óscar Rubén Cornejo Cásares, and Melissa Padilla, 2019.

CC BY-SA 4.0

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Change_the_Subject_film_poster_cropped.png#/media/File:Change_the_Subject_film_poster_cropped.png

A notable example is the case of 'Illegal aliens': a subject term in the Library of Congress Subject Headings thesaurus. This terminology was used by librarians to describe content relating to undocumented immigration. In 2016 the subject heading became a topic of political interest in the US, when a decision by the Library of Congress to replace it with the terms *Noncitizens* and *Unauthorized immigration* was opposed by conservative lawmakers. In 2021, the 'Illegal aliens' subject headings were indeed replaced with the headings *Noncitizens* and *Illegal immigration*.

In recent decades, mass digitisation practices have opened up CH collections to a broad and diverse public, including not only specialist researchers and scholars, but also different types of audiences and communities. As digitisation increasingly mediates the stories we tell ourselves and others about the past, CHIs need to reassess this set of issues. However, detecting and signalling bias is different for different stakeholders. For the collection owner, for example, bias becomes relevant and urgent when the collection is opened up and shared, whether physically or online. For the aggregator, identifying bias is often not even an option due to the sheer volume of data. End-users are likely to be unsuccessful in querying collections or finding relevant records if metadata is insufficient or inappropriate, or they may not always be aware of problems with the data. In this way, bias creates barriers to sharing, consulting and re-using content for all stakeholders.

1.3 Meanings and origins

1.3.1. Intentionality

Historical sources always come about from a particular viewpoint, in a specific setting, a certain timeframe. As historians often highlight, they carry an intrinsic bias. This also holds true for CH collections. When publishing digitised collections online, this historical perspective is often lost, while the bias remains.

When we look at existing CH collections and their metadata, we are often surprised by the bias encapsulated in the language used. Bias, in fact, seems so deeply embedded in the way we use words to describe what we observe in the world around us - and the digital realm as an extension of that world - that assumptions, stereotypes, outdated concepts and inappropriate terms are seen to permeate discourse even without the motive to harm. Therefore, a key question that comes up when dealing with bias in cultural metadata, is that of intentionality, which can be regarded as a sliding scale.

Intentional bias can be defined as terminology that is, for instance, overtly racist, homophobic or misogynistic. Very often, however, bias is found in humour that relies on derogatory or inappropriate terminology and reflects power imbalances (Tsakona, 2017, Ahmed 2017). While it can be assumed that intentional bias is present from the first stage of image and title production, it is important to bear in mind the age-old warning against the ‘intentional fallacy’ (Whimsatt & Beardsley, 1946): it is methodologically very difficult, if not impossible, to have certain knowledge about the intentions of speakers or producers of images and metadata, because they are structurally no longer there. Assumptions about intentions are therefore interpretations. Bias can be said to be **unintentional** when terms that had a more (perceived) neutral connotation at the time of production, metadata creation, revision or publication are no longer used, have been replaced or are perceived as biased (Moule, 2009; Gawronski, 2022). This type of bias can be present in the ideological framing of collections, in the attribution of metadata over time, and in the design of search engines and artificial intelligence (Hardesty & Nolan, 2021).

In the DE-BIAS project, the aim is to flag contentious terminology regardless of its perceived intentionality. This implies that we take into account current sensitivities, which in turn may evolve in the future. We therefore add the caveat that what is elaborated in the current *Typology* will need to be updated and reassessed in future iterations of the document or in new projects/contexts in which it is to be applied.

1.3.2. Historicity

A second, underlying problem can be qualified in terms of **historicity**: where do metadata come from? What processes have descriptions of cultural objects gone through - especially digital objects, which by definition have gone through several iterations of documentation and publication practices? In most cases, the full documentation trail is not even known to us: either the trail is incomplete, or the choices and decisions regarding the description and identification of cultural heritage materials were never documented in the first place. In many cases the bias lies in the silence of metadata: the descriptive elements are (un)consciously ignored, passed over by tradition or intention (Hilde, 2022). The presence of basic, incomplete or poor metadata is equally problematic: the lack of depth, precision or substance makes it almost impossible to assess whether the use of certain terms could be considered contentious or non-contentious.

An added complexity is that bias is not only expressed at the textual level (metadata), but also in the objects themselves (e.g. photos with stereotypical depictions) as well as in the relationship between text and object (Mowshowitz & Kawaguchi, 2002). In addition, external variables such as time, place, and particular context, which may or may not be explicitly referenced in the data, have a determining influence on the potential ways in which records are perceived by different users.

Nevertheless, the need and responsibility to be alert to and intervene in cases of bias remains, not only for collection holders, but also for curators, aggregators, researchers and other users of these collections (Holterhoff, 2017; Brown et al., 2017). In the digital age, as we rethink descriptive practices, including adding or producing layers of information to accompany and contextualise digital collections, we have a unique opportunity not only to not reproduce these silences, but also to externalise and counter the underlying message that these silences convey.

We have the power, the agency and the opportunity to do things differently. We therefore call on the sector to act, to join forces with heritage communities and to review controversial heritage collections before publishing online: re-visit, re-curate, re-frame where necessary or useful on the basis of the expressivity of digital objects and their metadata layers, the diversity of perspectives represented and the accuracy of representation. Revisioning should be carefully done to not lose the layer of metadata created under specific historical circumstances. For the purpose of versioning, the former descriptions could still be kept in the database with contextualising information.

1.4 Case- and Practice-Driven Approach

In this typology, we provide a framework to think about where and how bias can occur in CH collections. In compiling this framework, we have opted for a methodology tuned to the case at hand: that of aggregated collections in the context of Europeana and the common European data space for digital cultural heritage. Again, we need to add the necessary caveats. For one, in some cases, bias is found at the collection level, e.g. colonial collections and collections determined by older worldviews. Other collections are much more hybrid, e.g. newspaper archives containing different types of texts and data. Furthermore, problematic expressions must be considered as symptoms rather than causes of bias instances seen in CH. While a statistical-probabilistic analysis of collections would certainly open interesting avenues for research, we departed from the fact that Europeana is an item- or object-centred collection. This is why we have opted for an item-oriented approach that allows for extrapolation to a collection context. In this workflow, bias instances related to a specific item serve as red flags indicating that a CHI or its aggregator might want to take a closer look at the collection from which it originates.

While the design of the DE-BIAS project requires a word-specific approach, in this *Typology* we outline a more complex matrix that will provide a deeper understanding of types of bias by taking into account different levels at which bias is situated and by incorporating the theory of intersectionality developed by Kimberlé Crenshaw (Crenshaw, 1991; 1989). Using the DE-BIAS vocabulary as a starting point, we will develop an ‘axes of intersectionality’ matrix that will allow the application of our findings beyond the context of this project. In this way, we hope to provide the CH sector and its full range of stakeholders with anchors for reflecting on and addressing instances of bias in their own collection management and documentation practices.

In addition, DE-BIAS explores types and linguistic patterns of bias in metadata in the light of research already conducted on existing use cases and best practices. In different groups and cultures, various lists of bias are already circulating and widely recognised in policy-making, such as [Words Matter](#)³ (an annotated glossary published as part of a metadata project at Museum Wereldculturen, Amsterdam, 2016) or [Homosaurus](#)⁴ (created in 1997 by IHLIA LGBT Heritage, Amsterdam, as a Dutch and English thesaurus used as a stand-alone vocabulary to describe their collections).

3

<https://amsterdam.wereldmuseum.nl/en/about-wereldmuseum-amsterdam/research/words-matter-publication>

⁴ <https://homosaurus.org/>

The published version of the dynamic "Guide to Word Choices" [Words Matter](#), compiled by the National Museum of World Cultures (formerly known as Tropenmuseum, Afrika Museum, Museum Volkenkunde, and Wereldmuseum).

It is our firm belief that DE-BIAS should pay tribute to these existing works by incorporating them into our digital environment. This approach will be complemented by data from the test corpora we have studied, as well as insights from knowledge creation activities. By engaging hitherto under-represented or misrepresented heritage communities through community allies with sector-specific expertise as well as community roots or connections, we adopt the adagio: "Nothing about us without us", which is a crucial guideline in this context.

We do recognise that current communities and stakeholders may differ from historical communities bearing the same names. Their focus, attitudes and beliefs may have shifted towards other issues that are more important for the existence of communities nowadays. We also believe that, in addition to community involvement, it is also important to incorporate the voices of scholars with the expertise of the historical periods for the objects in CHIs. By combining different views and voices, we can revisit and build upon lists of bias, revising and updating them when and where applicable.

Finally, the field of application explored in the current *Typology* pertains to three specific thematic zones at focus in the context of DE-BIAS, namely a) migration and colonial history, b) gender and sexual identity, c) ethnicity and ethno-religious identity. Within each field, DE-BIAS has initiated a co-creative process with communities, recognising that values are the result of a social construction that takes place in each community in specific times, spaces and circumstances.

In smaller communities, such as indigenous or First Nations communities, meanings and biographies of objects tend to be known to stakeholders. Yet specifically for larger, dispersed communities such as Jews, the meaning of objects may differ depending on temporal and spatial characteristics of objects or events related to these objects. Stakeholders from some geographies may not know the meanings of objects from other geographies or periods. Scholars with the expertise in specific cultures are then needed alongside grassroots communities to understand political and social circumstances of knowledge construction in each case, to understand how the values associated with heritage are constructed, and therefore to externalise or otherwise reflect these values in the metadata attached to heritage collections.

Having established these fundamental concepts and considerations, we can now examine specifically where and how bias manifests in cultural heritage collections.

Section Summary

- CHIs face growing responsibility for metadata associated with digitised collections
- Bias in metadata needs attention especially as collections become available to wider, diverse audiences
- The DE-BIAS project provides a framework for understanding and addressing bias in cultural metadata
- Community involvement is essential in identifying and addressing problematic terminology

Practical Tips

- Start by documenting the metadata creation timeline for your collections
- Identify which communities are represented in your collections
- Establish relationships with community representatives early in the process
- Begin with a pilot project on a smaller collection to develop your approach

2. Where Is The Bias?

? Key questions answered in this section

- At what levels can bias appear in cultural heritage collections?
- How do linguistic and visual elements interact to create or reinforce bias?
- What role does temporal complexity play in metadata bias?
- How can we identify different layers of bias in collection descriptions?

As mentioned above, CH collections are often temporally complex. A first step - not always feasible due to lack of data - is to carefully identify the provenance of a collection and, where possible, to reconstruct the history of the metadata. While precise data may be lacking, it may be possible to identify or make assumptions about the creators, commissioners, and even archivists of certain collections, e.g. a collection started or owned by a religious order. Information about the historical and geographical location of a collection can be linked to dominant ideologies and is a first, broad basis on which to examine bias in the collection as a whole. However, as Europeana is entry-based and not collection-based, this step - although included in the DE-BIAS pilots - cannot be generalised to the general architecture of Europeana.

A second step is to identify the different data that are present, i.e. an object (in the case of Europeana this is usually an image or moving image, but it can also be text), a title (if any) and the metadata that have been assigned to an object, often at different times. This allows us to identify the level or layer at which bias may occur.

The three main possibilities are:

1. The **linguistic level**: the words used to describe an object in a collection (both the title and the metadata).
2. The **visual level of the data**: the representation and images of an object or the object itself.
3. The **relationship between the linguistic and visual levels**, i.e. the way in which and the perspective through which an object is described.

Fig. 1: Graphic illustrating levels at which bias can occur in cultural heritage collections.

While the DE-BIAS project works only on the linguistic level, there is a lot of potential to include the other levels as well, especially taking into account the rapid development of AI tools, as well as the necessity to include the parameter of visual information given that metadata to cultural objects can contain crucial voids. These could originate from metadata creators consciously or unconsciously ignoring certain elements or aspects of the object as well as from their lack of knowledge or understanding of adequate linguistic descriptors.

2.1 The Linguistic Level

2.1.1 Source Layer

At the linguistic level, distortion can be present in different temporal layers that are not always easy or even possible to distinguish. The first layer, or source layer, is that of the title or caption added at the time of production. The maker or commissioner has provided the image with a title or caption, often on the object itself (e.g. a handwritten reference on the back of a photograph), which is used as the source of the metadata or is visible in the image.

It is worth noting that such a source layer may not always be present, or may vary in scope and complexity. We tend to see different approaches here according to the

2.1.2 Additional Metadata

It is possible that in later stages of metadata creation or revision, further descriptors have been added to correct initial biases that are in turn perceived as offensive, hurtful and inappropriate by CH professionals, community members and/or the general public of contemporary users (Sinn, 2010). A good example of this would be the changing appreciation of the term 'handicap', which led to its replacement by the word 'disability', which was then also considered inappropriate and replaced by 'impairment' (as can be seen, for example, in the publications of www.disabilityrightsuk.org).

A Europeana gallery featuring depictions of disabilities in artworks across centuries, reflecting the diverse lives, experiences and treatment of people with disabilities. Curated with #DisabilityHistory twitter community.

<https://www.europeana.eu/en/galleries/9108-disabilities-in-art>

The more time that elapses between the creation of the object and the creation of the metadata, the greater the potential for bias to be transposed and propagated. Especially when collections are no longer isolated in the (digital) archive, but are decoded into audience-oriented narratives and adopted in public dimensions - including exhibitions, presentations and publications - these stacked linguistic biases emerge in all their complexity.

Examples:

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2051904/data_euscreenXL_1290993

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2051906/data_euscreenXL_https_www_openbeelden_nl_media_1240783

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2021653/https_www_archieval_nl_detail_php_id_41545059

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2051904/data_euscreenXL_1282289

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2051904/data_euscreenXL_961997

- Context: Historical material with multiple cataloguing iterations, showing evolutions in descriptive practices.
- Bias Analysis: The metadata show attempts to balance historical accuracy with contemporary sensitivity, illustrating the challenges of describing the content for modern media and audiences.

2.1.3 Digital Deliberation

Investigating bias in the digital realm comes both with opportunities and challenges. On the one hand, publication online means direct exposure: unless the publisher digitally curates every single object in their (often vast) collections, there is ample chance for imagery, wordings, and reasonings unfit for all audiences to trickle down the corridors of the digital content vaults. Such instances may go on to feed algorithms with amplified biases or might leave a persistent trail of unmanageable intrusion.

On the other hand, the digital ignites the power of the crowd as it provides a zone in which bias can be detected and flagged by a much wider range of users than would ever have been possible in the context of physical archives or repositories. By making digital records widely accessible, both heritage professionals and community members are empowered to flag bias and facilitate the timely identification of issues in further digital curation processes. This, in turn, helps to avoid conspicuous public exposure of problematic metadata.

The emphasis on storytelling, with the use of digital collections as narrative markers, currently evident in the practices of many CHIs and other (online) content producers, explores an inclusive approach to bias detection in order to prevent the ways in which contentious datasets are curated, processed, presented and referenced from causing further harm. Rather than an instrument to stir emotions into a swirl of societal upheaval, digital bias detection should be seen as a promising way to raise awareness, generate insight into the harm that words can cause and help to establish meaningful cross-community connections.

2.1.4 Shades of Misrepresentation in Nominative Data

While the project does take into consideration non-linguistic forms of bias, the main aim of DE-BIAS is to develop a digital search tool that can detect potential bias in the metadata of CH collections. To this end, we examined actual cases of bias in a number of Europeana records and several project partner collections. Our analysis showed that different types of bias are at play representing different degrees of misrepresentation at the linguistic level. For this *Typology* we propose a classification of the dominant types below.

Linguistic misrepresentation	
Misappropriation	<p>When a community-related term is used by non-community members to describe the community members' position, e.g., "Eskimo" or "Indian". Additional examples could be found in: the application of "Gypsy" rather than "Roma" or "Romani" or the colonial-era classifications of various Indigenous peoples.</p> <p>Example: https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2021009/5DF5BC4FA81DE75A477CE0C11B69E6CA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Context: Historical ethnographic photography from the early 20th century where Indigenous Sámi people were documented and labelled using the exonym "Lapp" or "Laplander" rather than their self-identified name "Sámi". ● Bias Analysis: The term "Lapp" and categorising people as "types" reflects a colonial anthropological gaze that reduces individuals to specimens of study. This approach to documentation was common in early ethnographic collections but fails to recognize the community's right to self-identification and cultural autonomy.
Stereotypes	<p>Assigns a rigid set of characteristics to a group at the expense of the characteristics and differences of individual members of that group. For example, a term is used to emphasise a stereotypical view, as in "a gypsy woman".</p> <p>Example:</p>

	<p>https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/08547/Museu_Provided_CHO_Stadtgeschichtliches_Museum_Leipzig_Z0046190</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Context: 19th-century portrayal of Jewish merchants, emphasising stereotypical characteristics. Bias Analysis: The metadata reinforces harmful stereotypes through descriptive terms that reduce individuals to caricatures of their presumed occupation or role. <p>Other examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.europeana.eu/en/search?page=4&view=grid&query=gypsy%20woman https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/199/item_76SZCPIQXBQUXMWXLZHKG3I4MICZVTQ4 https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/199/item_PGVMXMD5BMX2TOQ7UPIOWP7EKAI2G5HQ https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2024903/photography_ProvidedCHO_KU_Leuven_9988270970101488 https://www.europeana.eu/en/search?page=1&view=grid&query=old%20jew
<p>Outdated expressions</p>	<p>Like socio-political realities, ethics and conventions, language is constantly evolving. Expressions that are considered harmless and neutral in one era may later be considered inappropriate, reappropriated or redefined - and vice versa.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2022362/Royal_Museum_Greenwich_http_collections_rmg_co_uk_collections_objects_254735</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Context: Early 20th-century anthropological classifications using now-deprecated racial terminology. Bias Analysis: Use of terms like “negro” reflects historical scientific racism; while once considered neutral academic terminology, such classifications are now recognized as harmful and scientifically baseless. <p>Other examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/202/item_ERG3DSZXM5UUUVYF46UEYUZLNIADA4N4 https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/202/item_HBWTO4Z4MMTR7K43GTZUIO5AF3RJUVU

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/401/item_3MXN2SB75COQQ24SAKUNFLSZ5BCFXKCD • https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/401/item_QGBRK EBN5XHFITZWSCPP62LRGY56WGWD • https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/401/item_IKUIJK KA36CQMIOYYGCQM4WKRO2EI6CM • https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/401/item_ZBVWR CRZFNPOY2SDW44I76FWMJMPCLLC
<p>Derogatory language / dysphemism</p>	<p>Derogatory language is the deliberate expression of a low opinion of someone or something. It is often used to insult, demean or belittle with the intention of showing contempt or disrespect. Examples include racial slurs, nicknames, comments about ability, appearance or character.</p> <p>Example: https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/9200579/avuc4www</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context: Colonial-era photograph with deliberately belittling descriptions. • Bias Analysis: Use of intentionally demeaning terms that show contempt or disrespect, reflecting power imbalances between coloniser and colonised. <p>Other examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/2022362/Royal Museums Greenwich http_collections_rmg_co_uk_collections_objects_254735 • https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/916118/S_TEK_photo_TEKA0092979
<p>Diminutive language</p>	<p>Using words or forms that indicate a small size, degree or intensity. It may not always be deliberately harmful or even intended as disrespectful, but it can be interpreted as belittling. For example, suffixes such as ‘-ie’ or ‘-y’ (e.g. girly, lassie) or terms that suggest smallness or inferiority (e.g. little, wee, poor).</p> <p>Example: https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2021648/resource_document_collectiegelderland_L53NBS2GECSS2PDMB43WK3X5IS6EAMXIWUYYM5SHRF3IQE4WGA5A</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context: Casual reference attached to the popularised depiction of a woman in a professional role. • Bias Analysis: Use of diminutive terms often

	<p>infantilize or minimise the subject’s status.</p> <p>Other examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/90402/RP_F_00_5221
<p>Omission/erasure, selectivity and distortion</p>	<p>Without multiperspectivity, choosing a particular perspective distorts the situation or views.</p> <p>Example: https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/08623/20074</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context: Colonial photograph with metadata in which Indigenous subjects are unnamed while European figures are identified. • Bias Analysis: Selectively naming practices that render certain individuals invisible while prioritising others, reflecting power hierarchies. <p>Other examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/2032013/Ethnologisches_Museum_Staatliche_Museen_zu_Berlin_DE_MUS_019118_1869861 • https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/2032013/Ethnologisches_Museum_Staatliche_Museen_zu_Berlin_DE_MUS_019118_616090
<p>Euphemism</p>	<p>A term or expression used to replace words that are considered offensive or socially unacceptable. While euphemisms are sometimes used for humorous effect, they can also be used to mask harmful intentions</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>https://www.europeana.eu/en/search?query=Kristallnacht</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context: Historical descriptions of the November 1938 pogroms. • Bias Analysis: The use of “Kristallnacht” instead of “November pogroms”. The term “Kristallnacht” stands for a wave of violent pogroms against Jews that took place on 9 and 10 November 1938. Shortly afterwards, the term was used by the non-Jewish majority population and is said to have originated ‘in the Berlin vernacular’. The term was frequently used in Germany until the 1980s and is still used in other European languages today. It alludes to the broken panes of glass during the pogrom. As the violence was primarily directed against people, the term is

	<p>now regarded as trivialising.</p> <p>Other examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/90402/NG_2007_47_3 • https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/9200518/ark__12148_btv1b90495925
<p>Fragmentation</p>	<p>In metadata (as well as in images), minority communities are often singled out and isolated from other cultural communities and/or 'mainstream' contexts.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/2032013/Ethnologisches_Museum_Staatliche_Museen_zu_Berlin_DE_MUS_019118_1624689</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context: Ethnographic collection item where cultural context is separated from object. • Bias Analysis: Isolation of cultural artefacts or individuals from their broader community context, creating artificial divisions and losing important cultural connections. <p>Other examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/9200579/yprvga9f • https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/9200579/x24urczt • https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/2024904/www_top_foto_co_uk_Europeana_WEAVE_2002191_jpg • https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/15501/007802

While the expressivity of linguistic bias should not translate necessarily, directly or unequivocally into strategic decisions (e.g. with regards to prioritisation of bias instances), the graphic representation of the intensity of different 'shades' of bias given below can help to understand the impact of certain terms on collection users, and to envision the efforts needed by CHI staff to discover, recognize and address the most subtle forms.

Fig. 2: Gradient scheme setting out shades of bias on an axis of expressivity.

2.2 The Visual Level

The visual level has to do with what can be seen in an image (or a record). Here we can identify bias in the selection of what is depicted and how (Edwards, 2001; Sealy, 2019). In terms of the **subject matter** (a person, object or scene), factors such as selection and framing can be considered. As photography is a “technology of subjective decisions,” as defined by Sarah Lewis (2019), the adoption of specific visual techniques, such as framing, lighting, and posing, can be revealing, both implicitly and explicitly, of certain social and cultural biases). Often, we’re also able to visually detect the use of known stereotypes related to any of the axes of prejudice (e.g. sexism, orientalism, racism, anti-Semitism, etc.). Additionally, pictures or works of art could be examined for their use of (humorous) tropes or visual techniques (e.g. exaggeration of certain characteristics) that can be considered offensive from a common or a community-specific point of view.

In **composition**, the relationship between background and foreground, or edge and centre, can reflect hierarchical relationships. The use of lighting, colour and size, for example in the representation of ethnographic objects, can also reflect bias. Lighting, positioning, composition and sometimes manipulation techniques often removed objects from time and perspective and placed them in a liminal vacuum. This contributed to the creation of a space in which objects appeared decontextualised, stripped of their social and cultural meanings, and re-coded as scientific specimens (Edwards, 2001).

The ideological elements of formal representation can be related to the familiar notion of the ‘**gaze**’ developed in art history (Berger, 2008) and feminist film theory (Mulvey, 1975). According to this notion, there is no point of view that is not tainted by ideology, and the way objects are represented reflects power hierarchies and reveals ideological narratives. In fact, as shown in numerous studies (cf. Edwards (2001), Sealy (2019), Pinney (2011)), images can be seen as a powerful tool for detecting the dynamics of

authority and subordination. However, it is important to note that a purely visual analysis of the heritage material does not fall within the scope of DE-BIAS and this document. Rather, as indicated above, the project (and therefore the *Typology*) will look at the presence of bias in the visual narrative as far as it relates to the metadata level.

Examples:

<https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/9200579/avuc4www>

- Context: Colonial-era photograph showing intentionality with regards to composition, subject matter and gaze.
- Bias Analysis: Demonstrates visual bias through composition techniques - framing, positioning, and perspective choices that reinforce colonial power dynamics and racial hierarchies.

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2024904/https___www_topfoto_co_uk_asset_2928269

- Context: Illustration on the topic of migration.
- Bias Analysis: Shows how decisions with regards to how scene and subjects are depicted and framed can contribute to the 'othering' of subjects, reflecting the creator's cultural assumptions

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2024904/www_topfoto_co_uk_Europeana_WEAVE_1022304_jpg

- Context: Portrait photography using visual techniques to convey social status.
- Bias Analysis: Illustrates how compositional choices in background, dress, and positioning can reinforce social hierarchies and cultural stereotypes.

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2024904/www_topfoto_co_uk_Europeana_WEAVE_2002202_jpg

- Context: Photograph with deliberate staging choices in terms of suggesting personality traits and behaviours of the person depicted.
- Bias Analysis: Shows how photography can convey bias through choices regarding what is shown and how assumed narratives are shared.

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2024904/www_topfoto_co_uk_Europeana_WEAVE_2002233_jpg

- Context: Historical photograph demonstrating period-specific representational conventions
- Bias Analysis: Reveals how visual conventions of the period perpetuate stereotypical representations of certain groups.

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2024914/photography_ProvidedCHO_Ajuntament_d_e_Girona_341540

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/437/item_GQTYPBWR47VQLRL4W7TBAXGAWV5LYMND

- Context: Portraits using specific visual techniques for characterization.
- Bias Analysis: Shows how the use of light, pose, and framing choices can contribute to stereotypical or biased representations of individuals or groups.

2.3 The Relation Between the Linguistic Level and the Visual Level

2.3.1. Disparity vs. double bias

A particular type of bias lies in the relationship between the metadata and the image, i.e. in the way an object is described. This has to do with a disparity between the metadata and what can be seen in the image or, conversely, the way in which text and image reinforce each other in their (intended or unintended) expression of bias.

As for the first case (disparity), one dimension is what we described above as **nominative** bias: the fact that certain people or things are named and others are simply referred to by a general category. This can be seen, for example, in the image below, taken from the Europeana collection where both in the original image caption as well as in the metadata, one of the subjects (T. H. Parke) is clearly named, while the other is referred to as belonging to a general category - namely recognised simply as 'pigmy'.

Problematic record on www.europeana.eu. Direct link to object: <https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/9200579/zn9zbqfv>

Example:

<https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/9200579/zn9zbqfv>

- Context: Colonial expedition photograph showing both European and Indigenous people
- Bias Analysis: Demonstrates nominative bias through unequal identification practices - the European participant (T. H. Parke) is named specifically while the Indigenous person is referred to only by the generic and problematic term 'pigmy'

At this level we can also locate certain forms of **humour**, including satire, when the title or caption is clearly incongruent with what we see in the image. Besides the clear presence of derogatory terms and an overall strongly disrespectful representation of the depicted subject, the image also exemplifies how the certain contentious elements - both in the metadata as well as in the depiction itself - play a role in exacerbating certain forms of humour.

Example:

https://www.europeana.eu/nl/item/2022362/Royal_Museums_Greenwich_http_collections_rmg_co_uk_collections_objects_254735

- Context: Historical illustration with satirical or humorous intent.
- Bias Analysis: Shows how captions and titles can create intentional incongruity with the visual content, using humour to mask or reinforce discriminatory attitudes and stereotypes.

A further step is what we might call '**negationism**'. This type of bias arises from the fact that certain elements in a picture are ignored, negated or not mentioned. This leads to a hierarchy in which some elements are considered to be important, while others are considered to be superfluous and unimportant, and are therefore rendered invisible.

From DE-BIAS community consultations held in relation to the Gender and Sexuality theme specifically, 'absence' indeed emerged as the biggest element when dealing with Queer stories, highlighting the widespread invisibility and underrepresentation in existing collections. In many instances sexual preferences, relationships and personal attitudes are 'sanitised' and excluded in the metadata, and this makes it difficult for people researching queer stories to find the right content, and therefore to (re)activate meaningful stories. For example, words and paraphrases as 'good friends' were traditionally used to masquerade same-sex relationships, but this is something that the general contemporary public would not understand without the right guidance / historical context, and the paraphrase essentially 'negates' the understanding of the factual situation.

Example:

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2058401/_providedCHO_87a8a2c7_cfe3_4c2e_5394_e2cdc1517e12

- Context: Lack of descriptors creating absence of meaning.
- Bias Analysis: “Portrait of two men” could be intentionally or unintentionally negating a close relationship between the persons depicted.

In a similar vein, **omissions and silences** related to the Jewish origin of European artists may confuse the user. For instance, people may find it difficult to interpret some of the images related to Marc Chagall without the knowledge of his belonging to Yiddish speaking communities in the Jewish Pale of Settlement (Kizhner et al. under review)

Example:

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/270/resource_document_jhm_museum_M009245

- Context: Lack of descriptors creating absence of meaning and hindering full understanding of the scene depicted by the artist.
- Bias Analysis: While the metadata do describe the image as “In the foreground a couple in love with above them a protective (?) angel with a sword” there is no reference made to the importance to Chagall of the history and heritage of the Jewish community to which he belonged.

2.3.2. Confluence of meanings

While incongruence may introduce bias into our reading of CH collections, the duplication or confirmation of bias at both linguistic and visual levels may ignite or reinforce our perception of representations as biased. Stereotypes, for example, may be expressed in metadata that perpetuate stereotypes of culture, ethnicity or identity, while being carried through at the image level in representations that are one-dimensional or based on clichés. A similar confluence of meanings occurs in culture-centred or fragmented contexts. Descriptions may prioritise Eurocentric perspectives, using terms and language that reflect a Western-centric viewpoint, thereby vocalising what is implied in visual content disproportionately featuring Western cultures while marginalising others.

Example:

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/91609/SMVK_VKM_fotografi_112944

- Context: Dual-level manifestation of bias where stereotypical representations appear in both metadata descriptions and visual content, creating a reinforcing cycle of prejudiced interpretation.

- Bias Analysis: The combination of Eurocentric language in metadata paired with disproportionate representation of Western cultures in visual content marginalises other cultural perspectives and reinforces power imbalances.

Research into the values connected to cultural heritage in Europe has in fact demonstrated that those values have been shaped using dichotomies and juxtapositions, mainly between “us” and “them” in geographical, social and cultural terms (Da Milano (2019)). We see such instances occur equally frequently in colonial and selective historical narratives, cases of language- or culture-based exclusions, and ethnocentric labelling.

Example:

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/401/item_AMK2BVHUMFMHRCNNVO64Y7GCSLP4W4GU

- Context: Creating artificial divisions between cultures and communities.
- Bias Analysis: The dichotomies manifest through selective (re)presentation and ethnocentric labelling.

The relationship between the linguistic and the visual, it could be argued, creates its own matrix of intersectionality, where meaning is fluid and prone to change depending on how words and images interact. A word could make a seemingly innocent image controversial, a visual detail could turn seemingly neutral metadata into offensive expressions of bias. Either aspect alone might have remained harmless, unnoticed and undetected. It is only in relation to each other that the full narrative is achieved, and with it the toxicity of the content they convey.

Section Summary

- Bias can occur at linguistic level (titles, descriptions, metadata)
- Visual level bias exists in representation and framing
- Relationship between linguistic and visual elements can reveal additional bias
- Multiple temporal layers of metadata can compound bias issues

Practical Tips

- Examine metadata at all three levels: linguistic, visual, and their relationship
- Document instances where object titles and descriptions show disconnects
- Track the timeline of metadata creation and modification
- Pay special attention to terms whose meanings have shifted over time

3. How is the bias happening?

? Key questions answered in this section

- How do different types of bias intersect and reinforce each other?
- What role does dimensionality play in understanding bias?
- How can we use the matrix approach to identify bias patterns?
- Why is intersectionality important when analysing cultural metadata?

As we have seen in the preceding section, identifying and acknowledging the precise location of instances of bias can already help CHIs to address potentially harmful terms appropriately, depending on the stage or level of the documentation process to which the bias is tied. However, in order to develop bias mitigation strategies and apply tailored forms of remediation, it is crucial to understand the cultural, social - and in some cases historical - nature(s) of bias in heritage collections, and to recognise that bias is rarely one-dimensional.

3.1 Dimensionality and Intersectionality

In this context, the application of **intersectionality theory** to materials and documentation in CH collections can help us to appreciate the complexity of bias. By rejecting the idea that individuals experience only fixed forms of discrimination based solely on race, class or gender, intersectionality theory recognises the existence of a complex set of dynamics and interactions between systems of oppression and power structures.

The concept of intersectionality can be traced back to the theories developed by Kimberlé Crenshaw (Crenshaw, 1991; 1989) who, in the context of legal discrimination, famously noted how systems of oppression overlap and can reinforce each other because people are always defined by multiple categories: race, class and gender, but also sexuality, age, religion and (dis)ability.

Kimberlé Crenshaw, 2018
Mohamed Badarne - Heinrich-Böll-Stiftung.
CC-BY-SA-4.0

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Kimberl%C3%A9_Crenshaw_\(47078272734\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Kimberl%C3%A9_Crenshaw_(47078272734).jpg)

Recognising that positionalities in these categories intersect and overlap leads to a more holistic approach to addressing the multiple and overlapping forms of inequality and injustice in society. Thus, the marginalisation of women of colour cannot simply be considered along the axes of either gender or race and thus put on a par with the marginalisation of women or people of colour in general. Rather, the specificity of the experience (in a legal context, as in Crenshaw's work) must be seen as an intersection of race, gender, but also class, sexuality and age, and will be different for young or middle-aged women of colour, or for working-class or middle-class women of colour.

We propose to integrate the theory of intersectionality within a defined set of axes and parameters within the DE-BIAS project. This will allow to develop a fine-grained matrix supporting the identification of bias in metadata, while at the same time stimulating reflection on the complexity of bias as a temporal, localised and intersectional phenomenon. The matrix can also help users to search collections with different search terms and offer counter-strategies for signalling bias in the reuse of collections.

3.2 Categories On Axes: A Matrix Of Bias

Since the nineteenth century a number of relevant parameters have been foregrounded in relation to prejudice:

1. *Race*: a set of physical categories used to define groups of people (with the Caucasian position as the norm in many European collections) and subsequently

to associate a people with inferiority or even inhumanity. Today it is widely accepted that race is a social construct. However, having been racialised and shared common experiences of racism, racial identity is important to many and can be a basis for collective organising and support for racially minoritised individuals.

2. *Gender*: classification of people according to the binary opposition of male/female and stereotypical characteristics associated with normative masculinity or femininity, with masculinity being the dominant gender position in patriarchal societies.
3. *Class*: Hierarchical determination of individuals according to their position in society and the capital (economic as well as social, symbolic and cultural) or power they possess (Bourdieu, 1985). The most common division, from the position of maximum power to the position of maximum subordination, is that of the ruling classes or elites (nobility, religious and political leaders, the (upper and lower) middle class(es) and the working class). A newer class that has been added is the precariat (people in precarious economic or social conditions).
4. *Religion*: Identification of people as belonging to a religious group, according to a hierarchy in which a particular religion, e.g. Christianity, is seen as dominant and (implicitly) taken as the norm, and other religions are seen as inferior, foreign, barbaric or pagan.

In the course of the twentieth century, new salient categories were added.

1. *Ethnicity*: The identification of groups of people based on geographical location and/or culture (language and customs).
2. *Sexuality*: Classification of people according to their sexual preferences and practices as related to their identity, with adult heterosexuality as the norm.
3. *(Dis)ability*: Classifications based on physical and/or mental deviation from a norm of health or ability.
4. *Age*: Axis of classification of persons according to a division from child to adolescent, adult, middle age and old age, with adulthood as the norm.

In relation to the collections we studied on Europeana, other axes also seem to be relevant too, although they are less frequently mentioned in literature and perhaps more complex to determine.

5. *Civilisation*: The classification according to a perceived level of education and culture, with European culture as the norm.
6. *Geography*: Bias in the representation of geographical locations and centres of power, with both the West and the North seen as dominant, as opposed to the

South or the East (Anderson, 1991). In addition, the distinction between nature and culture (city) can be fraught with bias (Williams, 1973).

7. *Temporality*: The representation of historical periods and the distinction between modernity and primitivism.
8. *Gaze (positionality)*: The specific form of bias related to who or what is the object of the gaze and who is the beholder (Foucault, 1977; Berger, 1990; Mulvey, 1975).

The following visualisation sets out these categories as they developed over time and in the contexts described above.

Fig. 3: Grouping of categories considered relevant for examining intersectional bias in cultural heritage collections.

3.3. Fluidity vs. applicability

In future iterations of this document the authors might want to review the proposed categories of bias together with a wider stakeholdership radius of collection owners and aggregators, and community representatives. The wording may be reviewed and, based on an assessment of applicability/relevance to their collections or changes may be made to the set of categories. At the time of its (first) publication for use by the CH sector, the *Typology* as well as *Vocabulary* adhere to the mainframe defined in the section above, as it has proven to be a meaningful and effective instrument to approach the themes and collections at hand, as testified by the set of use cases below.

Use case 1 - colonial depictions:

In photographic collections

In colonial photography, for example, we see that bias is very often the strongest at the intersections of race, ethnicity and religion, but that the axes of civilisation, geography and gender should also be taken into account. Within this type of representation, it is common to see spatial/temporal dichotomies, usually highlighted by discrepancies in dress codes. Indeed, we often see individuals portrayed with their native 'primitive' garb, and colonisers with their usual garments (Amkpa, 2012). This marks a distinction between a modern temporal space - represented by the colonisers - and a 'primitive' temporal dimension. As metadata on photographic collections are often based on but not always in sync with the image and can be optimised to better reflect what is at play in the content, it is important to take this interplay on board.

In audiovisual collections

The Surinamese community that worked in the scope of DE-BIAS on the colonial theme could be identified along different lines of intersectionality like ethnicity, gender, age, class and religion. These differences in backgrounds played a role in analysing the metadata of the audio-visual material. For instance there was a videoclip in which the subject of 'Kruidendokter' was discussed in a derogatory way. Not everyone in the group analysed the bias in the metadata of the clip in the same way and there was a discussion on which terms should be used in the description. Part of this was because of the fact that not everyone had the same knowledge of this subject. Some of the group members had experienced it in Suriname and for others it was completely strange. There was also a clip in which the description mentioned 'Hindoestaan' instead of 'Hindustaan'. This also led to a discussion about term and notation. Here, among others, differences in ethno-religious backgrounds played a role.

Use case 2 - anti-Semitism:

With regards to the expression of anti-Semitism in cultural metadata, intersectionality is at play far beyond the commonly presumed areas of ethnicity and religion: it also

includes homophobia, racism, nationalism and even sexism. Analysing and assessing anti-Semitism in cultural metadata therefore requires a fine granularity in research and a broad framework of understanding, taking into account that anti-Semitism is an integrating ideology that works across opposing belief systems, social stratospheres and political camps.

Use case 3 - gender and sexuality:

When examining gender and sexuality in cultural metadata, intersectionality becomes particularly evident in how descriptive terms overlap with class, age, and professional status. Historical collections often show complex layers of bias in how women and LGBTQ+ individuals are described, particularly in professional or artistic contexts. For instance, in art collections, women artists are frequently identified primarily by their gender (“lady painter”) or their relationship to male artists (“wife of”), while their male counterparts are simply described by their profession. This demonstrates how gender bias intersects with professional status and social class. This type of intersectional bias is particularly complex because it often reflects historical social norms that may not have been considered biased at the time - or at least not in the same way they are today. For contemporary catalogers, this presents a challenge: how to preserve historical context while providing more inclusive and respectful metadata that acknowledges both gender identity and professional accomplishment.

3.4 From Understanding To Application

As pointed out above, the first step of carefully determining the origin and context of a collection will make it possible to draw out links with an ideological framework, which in turn can help to reveal certain types of intersectionality⁵. Moreover, certain determinants will take on different meanings depending on the collection itself. The combination of provenance research, collection profiling, intersectionality patterns, and an assessment of the nature of expressions of bias (see below) can reveal recurring patterns within a particular collection and its related materials. A combination of such analyses will allow for the design and implementation of a debiasing strategy depending on the frequency of bias occurrences, the prevalence of certain types or patterns of bias in an institution’s core collections, and the expressive weight of the linguistic misrepresentations

⁵ In this context, it is relevant and important to note the increasing efforts of CHIs to invest in provenance research for culturally and historically sensitive/controversial collections, such as those acquired in a colonial context. A good example of this is the MAS (Museum by the Stream) in Antwerp, which preserves Congolese heritage that became the property of the city. How did this collection of some 5,000 cultural objects come about? The provenance has been mapped during a two-year research project carried out jointly by Congolese heritage specialists and partner organisations FARO, the Royal Museum for Central Africa (Tervuren) and KADOC (Leuven). An introduction to the scope, objectives and status of the project can be found at <https://mas.be/en/herkomstonderzoek-congocollectie>.

encountered (cfr. 2.1.4 *Shades of Misrepresentation in Nominative Data*). With regard to the second step of linking nominative and visual bias, intersectionality will be helpful in identifying bias in the relationship between metadata and objects. Furthermore, bearing in mind that these categories can be placed on axes, it could also help to determine primary and secondary bias, or degrees of bias. Finally, a visual presentation of this workflow can assist both collection holders and users in assessing and interpreting the problematic/sensitive nature of particular collections, specific objects and specific terms.

To that end, the project team developed an instrument based on the present typological framework, intended to serve as a discussion tool for institutional as well as community-based teams profiling digital heritage collections or analysing specific items or instances of bias. The successful implementation in the co-creative workshops organised in collaboration with different community focus groups as well as capacity building events (both online and on-site) has strengthened our intention to make it available to the widest possible remit of stakeholder for further use at their discretion.

Fig. 4: Design of a circular matrix aiming at understanding bias in collections, objects and terms.

The ‘wheel of bias’ was developed as a stand-alone tool for bias evaluation in Cultural Heritage collections and as such could be used to assess and prioritise counteractions

against instances of bias, according to the gravity, intensity and degree of bias encountered either in specific records or on a collection level. By adding markers to specific zones of the graph - showing vertical sections according to categories of bias and circle layers to represent the severity or frequency of the bias found - CHIs, stakeholders and community members gain insight into issues of problematic language use and prioritise and strategise responses.

In the context of workshops, it proved to be a useful discussion tool, facilitating enhanced participation and engagement of the community focus group. Participants were required to critically observe a series of images taken from the Europeana collection as well as the words used to describe them. They were then asked to classify them on the 'wheel of bias' according to the occurrence, intensity and form of bias or misrepresentation. This was followed by a discussion of the workshop's results and of the participant's impressions.

With these methods, tools and frameworks for understanding and detecting bias established, we can now turn to practical considerations for creating more inclusive cultural metadata. This involves moving beyond simple identification to implementing sustainable solutions that respect both historical context and contemporary sensitivities.

Section Summary

- Bias often occurs at intersections of multiple categories
- Historical context significantly impacts interpretation of bias
- The matrix approach helps identify complex patterns of bias
- Community consultation is crucial for understanding impact

Practical Tips

- Use the intersectionality matrix as an analysis tool
- Consider multiple perspectives when reviewing potentially biased terms
- Document the full context in which problematic terms appear
- Consult with relevant communities about terminology preferences

4. The Way Forward - Towards More Inclusive Cultural Metadata

? Key questions answered in this section

- What alternatives exist to simply removing problematic metadata?
- How can we preserve historical context while addressing bias?
- What role should communities play in metadata revision?
- How can institutions implement sustainable solutions for addressing bias?

In seeking to identify instances of bias in cultural metadata, our research has highlighted the importance of a nuanced and forward-looking approach such as the one championed by the DE-BIAS consortium. While it may be tempting to delete or rectify metadata that contains harmful language, such a strategy risks perpetuating a historical oversight that impedes our progress towards a more inclusive and equitable representation of CH. Removing problematic language without providing context or acknowledging historical bias inadvertently obscures the lessons embedded in our collections. It obscures the opportunity to learn from past mistakes and hinders our ability to promote a full understanding of diverse cultures. Furthermore, such an approach risks running into problems again very soon, as biases are constantly changing and evolving.

At the same time, there is a consensus that some terminology can no longer be perceived as neutral, and that working with thesauri makes it possible to detect terminology on a large scale. Rather than erasing evidence of bias, we argue for a more constructive and sustainable solution that takes into account historicity and intersectionality to achieve a more fine-grained detection. In implementing the tool, we used existing lists of words (cfr. the section *Glossaries*) that have been compiled by different communities and are widely accepted. These were supplemented with our own lists (as represented in the DE-BIAS Vocabulary) based on the metadata we found. However, in order to provide accurate feedback, it is crucial that communities are actively involved in creating contextual information, as they are the most attuned to offensive language and can also suggest best practices for signalling and dealing with it, ranging from substituting terms to using quotes or adding context.

From the photo exhibition organised by the Youth Committee of the Cyprus Maronite Welfare Foundation, as part of the Kormakitis Green Festival, which took place on July 7, 2013 at the Kormakitis Community/Cultural Center. Cyprus Maronite Welfare Foundation, 2013.

CC BY-NC-SA

https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/2021732/KORMAKITIS_TRAD_37

By prioritising community contributions, we not only empower diverse voices, but also tap into a wealth of knowledge and perspectives that enrich our understanding of cultural artefacts. Communities have invaluable insights into the meaning, significance and context of their own CH. Embracing their contributions allows us to weave a more accurate and authentic narrative, filling in gaps and dispelling stereotypes.

In essence, our proposed approach is not to erase the shadows of bias, but to shine a light on them through collaborative efforts. Tools for detecting bias in large corpora of data are only a first step, and must always be linked to and evaluated by community-driven contributions. The involvement of experts is a key consideration as well: the nuances of historical bias represented in clichés and expressions from the past may be unfamiliar to communities, rather being the realm of experts who know temporalities, locations and intersectionalities. By installing multiperspectivity as a driver in the entire metadata analysis, creation, and revision process, we can cultivate dynamic and evolving cultural metadata frameworks that reflect the complexity and richness of heritage. This approach not only acknowledges the mistakes of the past, but actively demonstrates our commitment to a more informed and inclusive representation of cultural diversity.

Building on these approaches to creating more inclusive metadata, we can now synthesise our findings and provide concrete recommendations for cultural heritage institutions moving forward.

Section Summary

- Deletion of biased metadata is not the solution - context and transparency are key
- Community involvement is essential for meaningful metadata enhancement
- Tools for bias detection should be combined with human expertise
- A multi-layered approach to metadata allows preservation of historical information while adding contemporary context

Practical Tips

- Preserve original metadata while adding contextual layers
- Document the reasoning behind metadata changes
- Create workflows that include community consultation
- Build relationships with relevant communities before beginning metadata revision
- Consider implementing version control for metadata changes

5. Conclusions and recommendations

The present *Typology* serves as a guide for cultural heritage practitioners to help recognise and analyse bias within cultural metadata. By delving into the intricate dimensions of intentionality, dimensionality, and intersectionality, this framework seeks to further an enhanced understanding of the various forms bias can take in the descriptions of cultural collections. Through an exploration of academic literature and an examination of Europeana content, we have identified common issues and highlighted the levels at which bias tends to manifest.

The value of this *Typology* extends beyond mere identification, presenting itself as a resource for practitioners seeking to mitigate, prevent, or address bias in their own collections. The graph derived from our research provides a practical tool for analysis, assessment, and targeted intervention. Cultural heritage practitioners and stakeholders can leverage this resource to navigate the complex terrain of bias, allowing for a more nuanced and informed approach.

Furthermore, we emphasise the importance of incorporating the viewpoints and methods described in the *Typology* into the daily practices and ongoing efforts with regards to Diversity and Inclusion of CHIs. Creating a bias mapping with use of the graph, compiling a thesaurus of their own or building upon existing resources - including the Vocabulary published alongside this report - will enable CHIs to document and track instances of bias within their collections as well to systematically address issues detected. This not only enhances transparency but will also feed into a continuous process of improvement.

In essence, this *Typology* stands not only as a testament to the critical examination of cultural metadata but as a catalyst for positive change within cultural heritage institutions. By adopting and adapting the proposed framework, practitioners can contribute to a more inclusive and accurate representation of cultural narratives, fostering a richer understanding of our shared heritage.

Against this backdrop we add the following recommendations:

- We reiterate the call to action for CHI institutions and collection owners in general to revisit their collections with a view to reading metadata (and images) through the lens of bias detection.
- We strongly recommend that such a revisit be designed and carried out in collaboration with communities and scholars, in order to build insight and

expertise in identifying instances of bias, and to develop mitigation or counter-strategies that are supported by the communities to whom they relate.

- We support the complementary use of AI to more easily and frequently identify biased expressions; AI is a valid means to process large amounts of (meta)data and to initially flag patterns of bias that appear to be occurring. However, due to the complexity of bias expression and detection, a human-in-the-loop approach is absolutely essential. This human factor ideally includes both professional CHI staff and representatives of the communities affected by the identified bias.
- We recommend that, based on such interactions, metadata should never be omitted or obscured, but - on the contrary - added to existing descriptions, thereby enabling
 - Communities to gain agency over the narrative of their heritage,
 - Collection owners and visitors to gain insight into the pervasiveness of incomplete or misrepresented narratives.

Building on the insights and frameworks presented in this typology, the DE-BIAS project has developed two complementary and separately published sets of recommendations. The first addresses policy makers, focusing on strategic initiatives and structural changes intended to support the sector in combating bias in cultural heritage metadata. The second set provides practical guidance for cultural heritage institutions, offering concrete steps and methodologies for identifying and addressing bias in their collections.

These recommendations translate the theoretical understanding developed in this document into actionable measures, recognising that meaningful change requires coordinated effort at multiple levels. From daily cataloguing practices to long-term policy decisions, each stakeholder has a crucial role to play in creating more inclusive and respectful cultural heritage documentation.

Zotero bibliographic resource

A set of references to relevant literature, focusing both on the main theories and concepts explored in the text, and on specific use cases and biased expressions in the field of the 4 communities involved in the DE-BIAS project. This bibliography can be found on Zotero [here](#).

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